

IMPLEMENTING AN AVATAR GESTURE DEVELOPMENT TOOL AS A CREATIVE EVOLUTIONARY COLLABORATIVE SYSTEM

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Abstract

In this paper a system for the interactive generation of avatars gestures is described. The gestures are generated from a genome. The system uses a procedure that can be viewed as a cumulative selection process. The cumulative selection accumulates small changes. Since the selection acts in parallel on all the avatar mobile parts, the small magnitude of the changes is more than compensated by the fact that it acts in parallel on all the avatar parts. Describing the gesture by means of a genome, apart from the possibility of evolution of the gesture under a selective pressure, has another important advantage: different avatars can share part of each other's genome information. This way gestures can be generated carrying some degree of similarity. The similarity appeals to users because it allows them to share only some characters of the gestures while preserving one's identity.

1 Introduction

Designing gestures for artificial agents has been, up to now, mainly accomplished by means of labor intensive processes performed by specialized, highly skilled personnel. In the entertainment industry this has been often done in parallel with the study of the relevant gesture that a human would have performed in a similar situation.

In the Amusement Project we started from the assumption that the user is the ultimate judge of the quality of an agent gesture. The possibility of a collaborative process, between a user and an algorithm, using as a selective pressure an arbitrary fitness value, given by a user, and a mutation process given by an algorithm, has been introduced in (Dawkins, 1986.) In (Dawkins, 1986) the focus was on the evolution of only the morphology of the artificial creatures, our work is oriented towards extending cumulative selection techniques for the generation of gestures and behaviors.

2 State of the Art

There has been recently a certain number of experimentations about putting some sort of "Artificial Life" in particular, into avatars, and in general into artificial creatures. The evolution of artificial creatures (that, in the following cases, are by no means avatars) has been studied for example by Karl Sims (Sims, 1994) and Steve Grand (Grand, 1997.) We will analyze here briefly those two works.

Adaptability of genetically inherited autonomous behavior has, in the work of Sims and Grand, two different meanings. Both meanings further differ from the one adopted by us in the Amusement project.

Grand's creatures inherit a neural structure capable of (Hebbian) learning.

Sims's creatures, on the other hand, inherit a neural structure that is only capable of a behavior that is fixed for any given individual through all its life span. In other words: one has to wait for next generation in order to have behavioral changes.

Our approach is based on neither of the above. Instead it is based on the cumulative selection of small changes as described in (Dawkins, 1986.) In the Amusement Project we have tried to apply the principle of cumulative selection to the development of believable avatar gestures and behaviors. At this stage of the project we have successfully applied the principle of cumulative selection to the generation of gestures only. In the next months we will extend the model to include true behaviors. That is, we will have the gesture triggered by a stimulus. The correspondence between stimulus and response that we have defined as a behavior as in (Kosko, 1992) will be evolvable as well. This work, however, will report only the part relevant to the gesture generation.

As far as other research done in the field of autonomous agents is concerned, we think that it is important to look at two other approaches that are, only superficially similar to ours,

instead they are radically different in their underlining philosophy.

There is, for instance, on one hand, the research about autonomous agents capable of emotions "Believable Agents" (Bates., 1994) or the agents of Sloman (Sloman, 1996.) On the other hand, there is the need of the people "on line" to express themselves through an avatar.

It is important to stress that, in the Amusement project, one of the goals is to study ways of relieving the user from the burden of developing all the details of expressing one's own emotions by means of an avatar's behavior and appearance. Hence the autonomy of the avatar is not an end in itself. It should not therefore, be compared with the more sophisticated autonomous agents described in literature. The autonomy is not the goal. The goal is the expression of the human being that lies "behind the screen". Up to now, in the "Palace" for example, (Bumgardner, 1996; Suler, 1996) it was possible to express one's own mood only in a simple, albeit effective, way by means of switching between avatar static representations that were constructed beforehand.

Our work in creative evolutionary systems has centered around avatars used in a virtual environments. We have designed and implemented avatars which have an evolvable internal genetic structure. This means that their bodies' movements and outward appearance is not fixed, but changes under some selective pressure. These avatars not only can evolve but also, share genes with other avatars in the virtual world. This second aspect of genetically controlled entities has been, in our view, somehow overlooked. We are highly compelled by both of those two ideas, given its implications for optimal system efficiency, user-cooperation, creativity, and freshness of user-representation.

Each avatar has its own set of genes. Unlike a living creature, however, only three aspects of the avatar's persona are informed by its genes:

1. its gestures,
2. its physical shape, and
3. its texture.

At the first meeting of an avatar and its user, these three aspects above would depend simply on the avatar's default gene set. Therefore, the first task a user must perform is to help the avatar evolve, to refine its default phenotype into new gestures, shape and texture.

Let us explore avatar evolution in the realm of gesture. The avatar already has a set of gestures which result from the gene set it has by default. The user can generate new gestures by means of two mechanisms:

1. Offspring generation. In this scenario, the user watches as several of copies of his own avatar perform different gestures. (Copies are

necessary so that the user can watch his avatar performing many different gestures simultaneously.) The user chooses the avatar and gesture that most pleases him, or that best expresses an emotion he/she wishes to exhibit. From the chosen avatar and gesture, a series of offspring avatar copies and gestures are generated by means of a genetic engine. The genes in the avatar that created this gesture are thus transmitted to the offspring who all have the capacity to perform this gesture with small variations. This procedure can be repeated ad infinitum until the user is pleased with his avatar's gesture evolution.

2. Hybridization enables gene sharing, or cross-over, to occur. In this scenario, a user admires a gesture in another user's avatar, and uses the genetic engine to select that gesture and import it on his own avatar's gene set.

The evolvable avatars enable some key advances in Virtual Environments (VEs):

First, the user no longer has to specify every action they want the avatar to execute; they can create gestures on their own. This frees the user up to focus on the game or the conversation, and eliminates one of the inconsistencies between reality and virtual reality. For the industry, it is a breakthrough that these avatars (that have movable heads and facial features including the eyes, eyebrows, and lips) can automatically express the user's emotions because they have been trained by the user to do so. Creating an expressive face has historically been an extremely labor-intensive process; now it is fast and user-generated.

Secondly, hybridization (gene sharing) is an important creative and cooperative act. Heretofore, when something pleased us, we had only two choices: making an exact copy of an existing entity or building it from scratch. Gene-sharing, however, lets you take the essence of something that you like and add just that to your own gene pool, which may or may not create a discernible external effect, but in general it does. It is a way to promote sharing among users without dipping into the territory of direct cloning and its pitfalls.

We think these points of efficiency, hybridization, and collaboration represent important steps for our research.

3 System description

Avatars who are in our Active Worlds' world "Amuse" and "Amuse 2" move driven by users instructions (via mouse or other pointing devices) or by internal logic or both, depending on functioning mode selected. We have defined three different modes called mode 1, 2 or 3 respectively. Except for debugging and

3.4 Formal discussion of the internal model

The generic internal model is illustrated in fig. 1. In order to explain the workings of the internal model, we will describe it from the point of view of a generic user.

The user sees the avatar's physical appearance, the displacements and rotations of its whole body *inside* the environment. Such displacements and rotations are called *movements*. Moreover, the user can see the rotations of the various body segments of the avatar. A given set of such rotations is called a *gesture*. During a session in a Virtual World what the user perceives is a combination between movements and gestures.

The user, in turn, can interact with both the environment and the avatar by means of a generic pointing device.

The model has also an internal state that, for the sake of simplicity, we have limited, in this first part of the Amusement project, to the following variables: x, y, z, p (three cartesian coordinates of the avatar's position plus the angle of pointing.) The model accepts two sub-sets of inputs: the user inputs (USR), and the other avatar position and pointing (USR). The transition from one state to the next is regulated by the clock CK1. The CK1 frequency is usually a sub-multiple of the framerate. The framerate is the frequency at which all the scene rendering is recalculated. Typically the framerate is 10 fr/s. The CK1 frequency is usually 1 Hertz, i.e. 1 every 10 frames. The outputs are generated from the inputs by means of four fundamental functions called IO, SO, IS, SS. The gestures are selected from an ordered, finite cardinality, set by the output by means of the OG function. The output from IO and SO, and from IS and SS, is compounded by means of the operator which does not necessarily have to be a sum.

The structure of IO, SO, IS, SS can be diversified, we will discuss only the implementations that are relevant to our application.

Before proceeding we will introduce some little modifications to the model adopted in fig. 1. The relevant schematic diagram is illustrated in fig. 2.

In this new version the two sub-sets of the input, USR and USR, have been made explicit. Moreover, the following transforms have been applied, taking into account only the "horizontal" coordinates x and z . The vertical y coordinate is ignored.

The variable t is the total time of interaction and is calculated by summing the CK1 intervals where d and φ are defined as follows:

$$\varphi = \rho_2 - \rho_1$$

$$d = \sqrt{(x_2 - x_1)^2 - (z_2 - z_1)^2}$$

3.5 Modes in detail

The simplest case of all is the one we have called *mode 1* (puppet mode, fig. 3.) In this case SG and SS are null. The link between the output and the input is, hence, direct. The next state, that is, the next avatar position and pointing, is specified directly from the user input as well as the predefined gesture to be performed.

In *mode 2* the avatar is, in reality, a fully independent agent usually called a BOT (taken from the well known word "robot"). The BOT is fully independent and the user has no *direct* way to interact with it. The output and, hence, the relevant gestures, are function of the state by means of SO only. The next state (in practice the next avatar position and pointing), is calculated as a function SS of the position of all the other avatars and/or the present avatar position.

In *low mode 3* the user specifies directly the next avatar state (in practice, the new avatar's coordinates), but the gesture is calculated using the state of the avatar.

In *high mode 3* the user can still specify directly the next avatar state. But, since now the function SS is present, the new state is a combination of both the user input and the avatar's "will".

The OG block has been made explicit in all modes for the following important reasons.

The OG is, among other things, the memory in which the gestures are stored, regardless on how they have been triggered and/or generated. The SO block is responsible of one the most important parts of the avatar model: the link between a situation, identified with what we have defined here as the "state of the avatar", and a gesture. We will call this association between the situation and the gesture a

"behavior" according to (Kosko, 1992.) The SO block implements the behavior function b.

4 Experiments and Preliminary Results

We have carried out a series of experiments. The hypotheses were tested are the following.

1. A genome of reasonable variable length (in the range of 500-1000 reals) can encode all the information needed for the generation of an avatar gesture.
2. A mutation selection process of the type discussed in (Dawkins, 1986) applied to the genotype-phenotype pair, where the phenotype is a gesture instead of a morphology, will result

on the user behavior in this type of cooperative system. All the results are preliminary and qualitative due to the fact that the system has been operational with sufficient reliability only very recently. Quantitative definitive results will be available in the next months. All the experiments have been repeated several times.

4.1.1 First experiment

A set of three digital actors has been implemented using avatars in mode 2. That is, they were fully independent bots. The "digital actors" program has been run on the same computer running the 'world' server for convenience, but could have been run on any machine on the Internet. Indeed on the third experiment the users used their own machine. A temporary buffer of the OG memory of gestures was cyclically read and the relevant gestures expressed. The actors were put in a row on a stage. If no user input was sent, they repeated the same gesture over and over again. Each digital actor had its own gesture. Each digital actor was identified by a label, that could have been set by the user at any time, (i.e. "digiactor") and a number: 1, 2, 3. Hence we had digiactor1, digiactor2, digiactor3. Each user could select a different external aspect of the digital actor. It is important to note that the external aspect could have been different from the one the user had at the moment of the

in the evolution of a "believable character" (Bates, 1994) gesture phenotype.

4.1 Description of the Experiments

In the following the three basic sets of experiments that have been carried out are described. Those experiments were aimed at testing the hypotheses and acquiring knowledge

choice. At this point the user could, by means of a fill-in form, choose the number corresponding to the actor whose gesture he had liked the most. Once the avatar-gesture had been chosen, the relevant genome was automatically selected accordingly and used for the generation of a new offspring of gestures by means of a process of copy with random mutation. The process had

been therefore iterated. When the user obtained a satisfactory result, he “finalized” the process by choosing the name of the avatar to which he wanted that gesture to enter in the “repertoire” of gestures. It is important to note that this name had not necessarily been the one of the avatar used as digital actor, nor the one of the present avatar used. Anyhow, we strongly suggested using for the training, an avatar similar to the one which one planned to evolve the repertoire. Furthermore, he had to specify the mood that was meant to be signalled by the selected gesture.

4.1.2 Second Experiment

A group of users were requested to cooperate in the evolutionary procedure. That is, the setup of the experiment was exactly the same of the first experiment except from the fact that three users were using the system with the same “authorization name.” Note that three is not the limit. The system supports an arbitrarily high number of simultaneous users. If the users want to act separately, all they have to do is use separate “authorization names”. If they want to

expressions, and sounds. In this sense the choice of a gesture is a game in itself in the full spirit of the Amusement Project.

This very same procedure could be used, in the future, for example as well for the cooperative development of the movement of robot arms between engineers especially if they happen to be in distant locations from each other. Or it could be used for purposes other than the development of gestures. Indeed we may have applied the procedure to any cooperative “building” process. The only constraint is that the process has to be formalized in the form of a phenotype-genotype evolution.

4.1.3 Third experiment

In the third experiment the concept of genome sharing has been tested. Users that want to share genomes have agreed on a specific gesture they wanted to share and a stage where they wanted to play. Users can agree on any place of the Amusement Center. They subsequently notified their will to participate, by e-mail, to the sys-admin that gives them a common authorization name and they therefore, launched the "Digital

cooperate they may share the same “authorization name”. We have called this, “authorization name” and not “password” because it is less formal and can be shared. The scope of this second experiment was to test the capability of the system to stimulate creativity in a cooperative environment. People could communicate among themselves using all the communication channels, verbal and non verbal, available in Amusement. That is, they could communicate via chat, body language, facial

Actors” program directly on one of their machines whichever they wanted, however, they had to agree on one.) They repeated almost the same procedures of experiment two. The only difference was that they had to use the hybridization feature first and only from then on, they, optionally, started an evolutionary procedure. In this experiment the initial genomes were not set randomly but, set as the genome of the gesture the users had previously agreed upon.

In spite of the simplicity of the procedure, the emotional impact has been high. The possibility to share a gesture is something that carried a strong feeling of belonging. After all, gestures are part of any common culture. In any given culture gestures, for a given purpose, are similar without being identical. It was, obviously, possible to make a straight copy of a genome and "finalize" it to some avatar of choice. In the next part of the Project we will experiment with the this option as well and see which will be the most popular, the "straight copy option" or the "hybrid genome option" .

Besides, it is worth noticing that "artesan" artifacts were unique in the past, albeit similar among a given group at a certain time. It was only with the Industrial revolution that things had to be made in series of identical items. Most of the industrial efficiency is in that. The drawback was in the absolute identity of artifacts.

There is hence a trade off between "equivalence" and "diversity". Both concepts have positive as well as negative implications. They can be seen as two opposite ends of the same spectrum. In nature no two individuals are identical but all belong to a certain species, group, or family. Species are not just mental categories. Organisms from different species have no fertile offspring and usually none at all. Indeed species can be defined this way.

5 Discussion

As it can be seen, the procedures have been reduced to a very low minimum. Most games overload users with rules, probably because otherwise, among other things, once the game is learned it is not fun any more. On the contrary, the spirit of Amusement is to keep the complexity of rules to a minimum, meanwhile allowing for everlasting changes and evolution. This has been obtained by shielding the users from the complexity of the underlying software, by means of a very simple and straightforward GCI interface.

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